

COMPOSITE MATERIALS WITH PEAK STRAIN MEMORY CAPACITY

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SUMMARY: As composite laminates find ever greater application in safety critical components, it becomes increasingly important to be able to measure the accumulated damage within these new composite structures. There has been no small amount of research into possible methods of monitoring accumulated damage, including piezoelectric patches, fibre optics, and even the intrinsic piezoresistive properties of carbon fibres themselves. Some of the problems encountered by the above methods include manufacturing considerations, as well as the complexities associated with some of the monitoring equipment needed to interpret damage levels. As an alternative avenue to the delicate systems above, a more robust concept has recently seen development, with simplified sensor equipment, and the possibility for smart element incorporation at primary manufacturing stage. The smart composite structural health monitoring system under development at the University of Natal is based on the embedding of metastable ferrous alloy wires or films within the laminate. Not only can these elements easily withstand post-cure processing temperatures, but correctly used may impart significant load-bearing capacity. The detection system is simple to the point of damage assessment being carried out by a person with no special training.

The metastable ferrous alloys under discussion may be classed as smart because they possess a metastable austenitic crystal structure at room temperature, but upon application of strain, this transforms to a thermodynamically stable martensite. The fact that the austenitic structure is paramagnetic, and the martensitic structure is ferromagnetic, implies that there are levels of magnetic susceptibility corresponding to the percentage of martensite present in the material. Because this martensite forms in proportion to the amount of strain incurred by the material, a correlation between peak strain and magnetic signature is possible. It should be emphasized that it is peak strain that is recorded within the material, because the transformation is irreversible. So, even if the strain level drops, the amount of martensite remains the same. What this in effect means is that the maximum strain incurred by the laminate will be recorded, and this corresponds to the level of damage experienced by the laminate. The levels of sensitivity attained by the sensor elements are directly affected by two parameters: the transformation characteristics of the material used as the sensor-element, and the sensitivity of the magnetic sensing equipment. Although strain memory alloys have been successfully developed and used in other structural health monitoring systems, there are a number of challenges unique to the application of producing a smart composite laminate, since the volumes of martensite produced within such small elements will be minute.

KEYWORDS: smart composites, strain memory alloy, structural health monitoring, self-damage assessment.

INTRODUCTION

The importance of damage assessment within composite laminates is evidenced by the attention it has received in recent years, within the research community. The incorporation of piezoelectric patches, fibre optics, and various other devices within laminates, have all seen research and development. These methods are, however, often hampered by complex damage detection systems, and or, difficulties with the embedding process. First studies [1,2] indicate that it may be feasible to use cost effective strain memory alloy elements embedded relatively easily at primary manufacturing stage, to accomplish the same goal of structural health assessment of laminates. The added advantage of a relatively simple damage interrogation system makes this method very attractive.

Since strain memory alloys rely on an irreversible crystallographic transformation for their smart properties, any structural health monitoring system based on this group of smart materials is a passive peak system. By “passive” it is understood that in contrast to active monitoring, a full-time power supply is not required, and data storage facilities are also not required. Instead, power is only necessary during the brief period when the sensor is being interrogated, and the actual reading is stored within the sensor itself. Unlike an active system where the data is lost in the event of a power failure, the metastable alloy stores the “peak strain” reading within the actual crystal structure of the material.

This considered, the concept of the passive peak strain sensor shown below in figure 1, suits the needs of many safety critical structures. Although the passive sensor is only activated when necessary this does not mean that only “slow” events can be monitored, or that there has to be a large time interval between measurements.

Fig. 1 Operation of a passive peak strain sensor element

In order to produce a smart composite laminate using the above principles, various issues require attention:

- Material development – although strain memory alloys are not “new” they are not available “off-the shelf” since their metastability can be engineered in tandem with the mechanical properties required, using alloy chemistry and processing.
- Assessment of various interrogation techniques and the sensitivity limits of these – the volumes of martensite produced will be quite small and therefore need a very sensitive interrogation device.
- The geometry of embedded elements – both thin films and fine wires will be considered.

- Manufacturing concerns – not only are restrictions placed on element manufacture since any method used must not prematurely induce martensite, but consideration must be given to the same factor during the embedding process.
- The influence of smart element embedding on the laminate properties – this must be carefully weighed since the presence of damage detectors should not implicitly induce damage mechanisms.
- Development of the optimisation routine for the determination of optimal quantity and location of the strain sensing fine wires within composite material.

SMART MATERIAL DEVELOPMENT

The development of a material capable of assessing its own damage level is already at a very advanced level. Strain memory alloys have been extensively studied for the past 5 years. The fundamental principle governing the unique behaviour of strain memory alloys is an irreversible strain induced transformation from one crystal state to another. The parent austenitic crystal structure is paramagnetic, while the product martensitic phase is ferromagnetic. The fact that the martensite forms in direct proportion to the strain experienced by the material means that a measurement of magnetic susceptibility could be directly correlated with the peak strain experienced by a component manufactured from strain memory alloy. A typical relationship between the percentage martensite formed and the strain experienced by the material is seen in figure 1 below.

Fig. 2 Relationship between strain and volume martensite

The metastability which essentially imparts the strain memory to an alloy, does not belong to a confined group of ferrous alloys; the formulation may be as simple as Fe-Ni, or as complex as Fe-Ni-Cr-Mo-Si-C-Mn, the most fundamental consideration being what effect each alloying element has on the austenitic stability of the final alloy. So, while elements such as Manganese, Nickel, Carbon, Silicon, Nitrogen, and Chromium may bring to the table, desirable physical properties such as strength, corrosion resistance, ductility, workability, etc. it is important to consider all of these in the light of which crystal structures they stabilise. Elements such as Chromium, which have a BCC structure, obviously tend to stabilize the BCC martensite phase, while elements such as Nitrogen, Nickel, and Manganese stabilize the austenitic structure (FCC). Thus, if one adds Chromium for corrosion resistance, enough Nickel, Manganese, Nitrogen, Silicon, or other alloying element must be added to allow an austenitic structure to exist at room

temperature, but still be metastable. Depending on the alloying elements used, the chemistry window for transformability may be very small, which is why precision alloy production is essential.

The purpose of strain memory alloys is primarily just that, their “smart” property, which means that we require an austenitic structure (not martensitic) at sensor operating temperatures (in the room temperature vicinity). Alloying chemistry must then be used to suppress the martensite start (M_s) temperature so that an austenitic structure is metastable at room (or operating) temperature. A thermo-mechanical processing technique known as Prior Deformation of Austenite (PDA) may be applied to the material impart higher strength by increasing dislocation density, but also to destabilize the austenite, making it transform more readily. However, although PDA may be applied to achieve these two things, it is not necessarily a compulsory step in the production of a strain memory alloy. There are applications where high strength is not a requirement, and the costly thermo-mechanical processing can be avoided altogether, provided that the requisite transformation characteristics can be produced using alloying only.

There are two variables to consider when applying a thermo-mechanical treatment to the material: the amount of work that will be put into the material, and the temperature at which it will be carried out, both of which have an influence on the final strength achieved. Obviously, the PDA must be carried out within the deformation range permitted by the TTT characteristic, but an optimum temperature can usually be found, which produces greatest strength. [3] As far as the effects of the amount of work, this may be directly correlated with the strength attained, as well as having an effect on the sensitivity of the material to transformation. Figure 3 shows results of a strain test wherein martensitic content (which has been measured via the magnetic characteristic of the Hall output) is plotted vs. strain.

Fig. 3 The Effect of Varying Amounts of PDA on Transformation Characteristics

Scrutiny of figure 3 produces the conclusion that increasing degrees of work produce greater sensitivity to strain, assuming that “A15” is the working name given to the alloy, while the index 0,1,2 etc indicates the level of work put into the material. For example, 0 implies that the material was not warm worked at all, while 4 implies that the material has seen an 80% reduction in thickness during a warm rolling process. What then becomes evident from figure 3 is that the more destabilized the austenite (i.e. the higher the dislocation density) the easier it transforms, the greater the sensitivity to strain.

Due to the fact that ultra high strength is not required in the sensor elements to be embedded in composite laminates, candidate materials were not given any thermo-mechanical processing. Two different alloys were formulated and small samples tested in tension, to compare their transformation characteristics. [4] The transformation, or volume martensite was indirectly measured by monitoring the changing magnetic

susceptibility. This was achieved by winding a coil around the sensor section. The inductance of the coil is measured, and any change in magnetic susceptibility in the core material will cause a change in the inductance measured. This is then translated a DC voltage. The results of these tests can be seen in figure 4 below, where it is evident that the Fe-Cr-Mn alloy produces a much smoother transformation curve, thereby yielding a more accurate indication of strain.

Fig. 4 Strain vs transformation for two different candidate alloys

DAMAGE ASSESSMENT TECHNIQUES

Various methods of measuring changing magnetic susceptibility have been considered, and researched against the stringent criteria of sensitivity, simplicity, and robustness. Among the techniques identified to hold promise in this regard, are the SQUID, and an inductance-based measuring method.

SQUID: (Superconducting QUantum Interference Device): The most desirable attributes of this device lie in the fact that it is both extremely accurate/sensitive, and already exists in an “off the shelf” form. The expense of this equipment can only be justified where one probe will be used to interrogate many smart structures, and the amounts of martensite generated are exceptionally small, making it perfect for the composite laminate application. The device consists of two superconductors separated by thin insulating layers to form two parallel Josephson (high speed) junctions. The phase changes in the two junctions, due to changes in the magnetic flux, cause oscillations in the SQUID current. The change in flux can be calculated from the number of oscillations. The flux is then converted to a voltage. The SQUID is one of

the most sensitive magnetometers known to man. It is however, also extremely delicate, extremely expensive, and quite cumbersome since it requires liquid helium cooling.

A modified inductance method:

Although the circuitry and method used to test the transformation characteristics of candidate materials was very effective, it is not feasible to wind coils around elements embedded in composite laminates, so a modification on the same theme was explored, using a probe containing a pancake coil, which is brought into close proximity with the embedded element, but is not physically connected to the smart element. The apparatus is described in some detail below, making reference to figure 5.

Fig. 5 Schematic of pancake coil apparatus

A Pancake coil uses the theory of electromagnetic induction to measure changes in voltage as a result of changes in impedance. It consists of an oscillator, L – C circuit and a voltmeter. An L – C circuit is characterized by oscillating current and charge. The angular frequency of oscillation is: $\omega_0 = \sqrt{\frac{1}{LC}}$. The circuit is driven by an oscillator, oscillating at ω_1 , the natural frequency of the L – C circuit. As a material is brought into contact with the coil the permeability of the material causes the natural frequency of the L – C circuit to change. This change is measured as voltage V_s shown in figure 6.

Fig. 6 The change in voltage V_s due to magnetic susceptibility changes

EXPERIMENTAL WORK

The initial tests for feasibility of the concept of smart laminate creation were carried out using thin film specimens with a damage concentrator to allow easy detection of transformation. [5] Flat tensile samples were then produced, some of which served as an experimental control (without embedded smart elements), and the rest of which would be tested to failure to check whether any transformation could be read, whether any damage was introduced by the presence of the smart elements, and whether or not delamination occurred rather than load transfer to the smart elements.

Two types of samples were therefore produced in the following manner:

- a) 10-layer fibreglass laminates, and
- b) 10-layer fibreglass laminates with embedded steel strips (140x3mm).

Prior to each experiment, fibreglass, vacuum bag, release ply and bleeder cloth were cut to required size. To prepare each sample, tacky tape was first applied around the mould and the surface of the mould polished with run-in wax. Resin was mixed in the proportion: Resin: Hardener mixture: 50g : 15g. The surface of the mould was wetted with resin before the first layer was laid. The layers were then laid, applying resin after each layer to make sure that all fibres are wetted. All visible voids were eliminated before the next layer was laid.

After the final layer, perforated release ply and bleeder cloth were laid. The set-up was carefully covered with vacuum a bag and then connected to the nearest vacuum station. After making sure that there were no leaks in the system, the vacuum pump was switched on. The pump supplied A 95 kPa vacuum pressure. Curing time was 1-2 hours, after which, the vacuum pump was switched off. Each sample was demoulded after 24 hours. In addition, each sample was kept in the laboratory for at least 7 days to allow for complete hardening before undergoing tensile testing.

The results of tensile testing are shown in table 1 below.

Table 1 Tensile test results for samples with and without smart elements embedded

<u>Sample No.</u>	<u>Strip (Y/N)</u>	<u>Load At Failure (N)</u>	<u>Ultimate Tensile Strength (MPa)</u>
1	N	8253	114.63
2	N	12090	167.92
3	N	7890	109.58
4	N	9072	126.00
5	N	12490	173.47
6	Y	11230	155.97
7	Y	10610	147.36
8	Y	12030	167.08
9	Y	9648	134.00
10	Y	11270	156.53

For samples 1-5, the average ultimate strength is 9959 N or 138.32 MPa, while for samples 6-10, the average ultimate strength is 10957.6 N or 152.20 MPa, showing that on average, the presence of the embedded smart element raised the UTS of the sample, and did not have any adverse effects on material properties. While the tensile tests were underway, the magnetic susceptibility was checked using the pancake coil apparatus described previously, the results of which are shown in table 2 below, and graphically shown in figure 7.

Table 2 Magnetic susceptibility changes due to strain induced in the composite laminate

<u>TRIP Steel Strip Sample No.</u>	<u>ϵ (%)</u>	<u>ΔV_1</u>	<u>ΔV_2</u>	<u>ΔV_3</u>	<u>ΔV_4</u>	<u>ΔV_5</u>	<u>Average ΔV</u>
1	11.11	14.4	20.8	42.2	49.3	53.0	35.94
2	10.77	16.0	20.3	37.0	43.7	53.6	34.12

3	5.74	16.3	17.3	30.0	48.7	54.4	33.34
4	21.62	20.0	24.7	42.0	60.1	64.8	42.32
5	19.66	14.6	21.7	40.8	34.6	58.2	33.98
6	3.77	12.4	20.3	43.2	33.7	55.1	32.94
7	27.70	17.7	33.3	57.7	68.3	67.9	48.98

Fig. 7 Change in magnetic susceptibility due to strain in composite laminate

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Initial studies would indicate that this technology holds a great deal of promise, and warrants further investigation and development. Although transformation was detected using the crude pancake coil method used in the laboratory, this instrument needs further development, and refinement so that the even smaller amounts of martensite that will be produced by embedding fine wires, can also be detected – a task not yet attempted.

The embedding of smart elements has the effect of imparting a degree of strength to the laminate, without adversely affecting material properties. The load on the laminate is effectively transferred to the embedded smart elements, and measurable transformation is induced.

Further development would include the manufacture of fine wires, the weaving of these fine wires into pre-forms, and the optimisation of smart element placement.

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